

Aircraft Maintenance Scheduling based on Digital Twins

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Abstract: The adoption of Digital Twins paves the way for transforming the traditional operations of the manufacturing domain into the new era of digitalization. The aviation industry is adopting cutting-edge technologies to reform the daily business operations of aircraft maintenance schedules, shifting to a new service-oriented paradigm. This paper introduces a Digital Twin based on Coloured Petri Nets to evaluate the performance and provide dynamic adaptation of the maintenance fleet scheduling strategies by incorporating possible disruptions in the maintenance schedule. Simulation results showcase the framework's efficacy by providing a 22.3% reduction in cost compared to a static maintenance strategy.

Keywords: Aircraft Maintenance, Digital Twin, Coloured Petri Net, Discrete Event Systems, Manufacturing as a Service

1. INTRODUCTION

The aviation industry is shifting from traditional operations to a new paradigm called Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) (Sharma and Singh (2017)). At the core of MaaS is servitization, where companies extend their production by offering services or resources to external customers temporarily. In the same direction, aircraft maintenance has again drawn the attention of researchers and industry (van der Weide et al. (2022)), as the digital transformation of the aviation industry (Tsakalerou et al. (2022)) enables innovative maintenance techniques aimed at minimizing operational costs and reducing aircraft downtime. Maintenance tasks are typically performed periodically, requiring repetition after a specific time interval. This interval could depend on the type of task, the operational requirements, and the current status of each aircraft (Deng et al. (2020)). Airline operators need to carefully design maintenance projects and select appropriate days to maximize the utilization of aircrafts and ensure the operational capabilities of the whole fleet.

However, within maintenance fleet scheduling, one of the main challenges is to deal with schedule disruptions in the sense of sudden maintenance requests that extend even beyond in-house operations. Therefore, anticipating and incorporating these disruptions to the current schedule is crucial to maximizing revenue and overall operational efficiency. Therefore, the state of practice for Maintenance, Repair, and Overhaul (MRO) activities is to utilize integrated digital tools to evaluate different policies for the aircraft maintenance schedule towards extracting feasible and cost-optimized maintenance schedules (Chandola et al. (2022)). However, one of the main challenges in aircraft maintenance is to incorporate unscheduled maintenance tasks without significantly altering the existing schedule (Rengasamy et al. (2018)).

In this context, Digital Twins (DTs) (Wang and Liu (2021), Xiong and Wang (2022)) are an emerging framework that can be used to optimize the maintenance operations and enable the servitization of MRO activities. By leveraging real-time data, DTs can provide novel methods that provide quantitative risk assessments for the optimal timing of aircraft maintenance, thereby reducing the costs and maximizing fleet availability (Bisanti et al. (2023)). The foundational block behind DTs often relies

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on modelling the underlying problem as a Discrete Event System (Vardakis et al. (2025)) to streamline the operation processes and offer guarantees for feasible fleet scheduling. Petri Nets (Lee and Mitici (2020)), and Coloured Petri Nets (CPNs) (Sheng and Prescott (2019)) have been exploited recently as the basis to build digital tools that effectively capture the dynamics of maintenance operations and evaluate different maintenance strategies.

In this paper, we design a DT based on CPN that serves as a virtual replica of the physical maintenance scheduling operations of an aircraft fleet. Specifically, the framework effectively models the maintenance schedule of an aircraft fleet over a time horizon and evaluates various maintenance strategies. The proposed DT enables a comprehensive analysis of how different strategies impact overall fleet availability, maintenance efficiency, and operational costs. The proposed modeling captures the dynamic behavior of maintenance tasks across the fleet, including their periodic execution requirements and resource constraints, thereby offering a robust foundation for adaptive and cost-effective maintenance planning. Moreover, the framework provides the necessary safety guarantees, while also being able to dynamically change the maintenance strategy depending on sudden disrupts and maintenance requests. Evaluation highlights that the proposed framework can provide timely adaptations by reducing the overall maintenance cost by 22.3% based on static strategies.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the proposed modelling of aircraft maintenance is introduced. Section 3 describes the CPN approach to capture the dynamics for evaluating different strategies for fleet maintenance schedules. In Section 4, the evaluation of the proposed framework is presented, while Section 5 concludes the paper and discusses future directions.

2. SYSTEM MODELLING

This section introduces the system modelling for the maintenance scheduling of an aircraft fleet over a horizon. Specifically, we consider an aircraft fleet that consists of m aircraft, $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_m\}$, and $K = \{k_1, \dots, k_n\}$ possible maintenance tasks. Each aircraft $a_i \in A$ requires the execution of several tasks $k_j \in K$. We consider the maintenance horizon H for each aircraft discretized in days: $t \in [t_0, t_0 + 1 \dots, t_0 + H]$, to track each aircraft's maintenance and operational periods. Let us define the following binary decision variable that denotes whether aircraft a_i is grounded waiting for maintenance or operational at time t :

$$x_i(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ aircraft is grounded} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Since maintenance tasks are performed periodically, let f_{ij} denote the maximum allowable operational time interval between two successive executions of task k_j on aircraft a_i . Moreover, d_{ij} denotes the duration of maintenance task k_j to aircraft a_i . Durations vary depending on the aircraft and the complexity of the task.

Furthermore, we define for each aircraft $a_i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ the vector $q_i = [q_{i1} \dots q_{in}]$ which indicates the time of last completion of task k_j on aircraft a_i . We introduce the variable $c_{ij}(t), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ to de-

note the elapsed time since the last execution of a task, $c_{ij}(t) = (1 - x_i(t))(t - q_{ij})$. As a result, $c_{ij}(t)$ is a clock between two consecutive executions of task k_j on a specific aircraft a_i . However, it must hold that $c_{ij}(t) \leq f_{ij} \forall i \in 1, \dots, m, j \in 1, \dots, n$, meaning that the elapsed time since the last execution of a task can not surpass its maximum operational interval. We emphasize that while grounded, the utilization clocks for all tasks are not incrementing, and this is the reason we included the term $(1 - x_i(t))$ in the definition of $c_{ij}(t)$. Moreover, an aircraft is permitted to execute the maintenance task k_j at time t only if the elapsed time surpasses a ratio of the maximum operational time interval, i.e., $b_{ij}f_{ij} \leq c_{ij}(t)$, where $b_{ij} \in (0, 1]$ is the ratio for the specific task. As a result, we define the binary variable $y_{ij}(t)$, to denote whether task k_j is enabled for aircraft a_i at time t :

$$y_{ij}(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & b_{ij}f_{ij} \leq c_{ij}(t) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

To distinguish the grounded state and maintenance state for each aircraft, we define the binary variable $z_i(t)$, as follows:

$$z_i(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ aircraft is under maintenance} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, when the i^{th} aircraft state is under maintenance at time t , i.e., $z_i(t) = 1$, then we also assume that $x_i(t) = 0$. Moreover, when aircraft a_i is under maintenance at time t , i.e., $z_i(t) = 1$, we define the maintenance project $r_i(t)$, as the set of all currently enabled tasks:

$$r_i(t) = \{k_j \in K : y_{ij}(t)z_i(t) = 1\}. \quad (4)$$

Moreover, we define $\delta_i(r_i(t))$ to denote the duration of the project $r_i(t)$ at the beginning of maintenance as follows:

$$\delta_i(r_i(t)) = \sum_{j=1}^n y_{ij}(t)d_{ij}. \quad (5)$$

Upon the project's completion at time t , for all the maintenance tasks that comprised the project $k_j \in r_i(t)$, the time of last execution is updated i.e. $q_{ij}(t) = t$, resetting their clocks $c_{ij}(t)$ to zero. Following, the aircraft returns to the operational state, i.e., $x_i(t) = 0$ and $z_i(t) = 0$. Finally, considering the operational requirements of the aircraft fleet A , it is required that, at any given time, the number of aircraft under maintenance must not exceed a predefined maximum limit, denoted by L . Therefore, the following constraint must be satisfied for all t :

$$\sum_{i=1}^m z_i(t) \leq L, \forall t \in [t_0, \dots, t_0 + H]. \quad (6)$$

3. DIGITAL TWIN BASED ON CPN

In this section, we first give a brief description of the CPN and then we define the proposed DT for aircraft maintenance based on the CPN structure.

A Petri net is a computational model designed to capture the dynamic behavior of Discrete Event Systems (DES) (Cassandras and Lafortune (2008)). Petri nets share similarities with finite-state automata by representing and simulating event-driven systems. However, we opted for Petri nets for maintenance aircraft because they can model system transitions, enabling them to represent complex

Fig. 1. Structure of the proposed CPN to highlight the states and transitions of aircrafts.

systems, which is crucial in scheduling problems like aircraft maintenance. CPNs are an extended version of basic Petri nets defined as a structure $CPN = (P, N, F, M_0)$, where (a) P represents the set of places of the CPN, (b) N represents the set of transitions of the CPN, (c) $F \subseteq (P \times N) \cup (N \times P)$ represents the arcs between places and transitions with weight equal to one, (d) M_0 represents the initial marking, defining the distribution of aircraft tokens across places. The dynamics of the CPN depend on the firing of transitions. When a transition is fired, it consumes tokens from each input place and produces the same number of tokens in each output place, the number of which depends on the weight of each arc. The firing of transitions updates the marking M of the CPN at time t .

3.1 CPN structure

Here, we present the structure of the CPN that we employ as the foundational block for the proposed DT.

Places: The places of the CPN are organized into five discrete subsets of places, as shown in Fig. 1, forming the set $P = P_1 \cup P_2 \cup P_3 \cup P_4 \cup P_5$. $P_1 = \{p_1\}$ represents the operational state of the aircraft. $P_2 = \{p_2\}$ represents the grounded state of the aircraft, where it is no longer operational and awaits maintenance availability. The places $P_3 = \{p_{31}, \dots, p_{3n}\}$ represent the selection of task k_j for execution during the upcoming maintenance project. $P_4 = \{p_4\}$ represents that the aircraft is under maintenance. Lastly, $P_5 = \{p_5\}$ represents the maintenance availability L .

Transitions: Similarly, the transitions of the CPN are organized into six subsets $N_1 = N_1 \cup N_2 \cup N_3 \cup N_4 \cup N_5 \cup N_6$, as shown in Fig. 1. $N_1 = \{\nu_1\}$ is the transition responsible for the propagation of aircraft from the operational state p_1 to the grounded state p_2 . Transitions $N_2 = \{\nu_{21}, \dots, \nu_{2n}\}$ represent the selection of task k_j for the next maintenance project $r_i(t)$ of aircraft a_i . Each ν_{2j} operates between place p_2 and places p_{3j} . The transition $N_3 = \{\nu_3\}$ is responsible for both the merging of the enabled tasks and the shift of the aircraft from the grounded place p_2 to the maintenance place p_4 to execute the formed project. Then, the transition $N_4 = \{\nu_4\}$ controls the shift of the aircraft from the under maintenance state p_4 back to the operational state

p_1 . The transitions $N_5 = \{\nu_5\}$ and $N_6 = \{\nu_6\}$ represent the time spent in the operational and under maintenance states, in the CPN places p_1 and p_4 , respectively.

Tokens: Three types of tokens are defined in the proposed CPN model. Tokens denoted by $\tau_{a_i} = \langle a_i, c_i(t), \delta_i \rangle$, where $c_i(t) = [c_{i1}(t), \dots, c_{in}(t)]$, i.e. the vector of the utilization clocks $c_{ij}(t)$ since the last execution of maintenance task k_j , $\forall j \in [1, n]$, represent an aircraft. The token identifier a_i corresponds to the i^{th} aircraft and δ_i is the duration of the next maintenance project $r_i(t)$. Aircraft tokens are related to places p_1 , p_2 , and p_4 , highlighted with red color in Fig. 1, representing the three possible states of any aircraft: operational, grounded, or under maintenance, respectively. The second token type for set P_3 is token $\tau_{k_j} = \langle k_j, h_j(t) \rangle$, where $h_j(t) = [h_{1j}(t), \dots, h_{mj}(t)]$ indicates that the duration of the next project should include the duration of this task in case it is enabled, as follows:

$$h_{ij}(t) = \begin{cases} d_{ij}, & \text{if } y_{ij}(t) = 1 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Tokens τ_{k_j} are associated with the corresponding places p_{3j} , denoting the task durations in the next maintenance project $r_i(t)$. The third token type for the P_5 set is token $\tau_\zeta = \langle \zeta \rangle$, where ζ represents the current maintenance availability. The maximum value of ζ equals L of Eq. (6), denoting the maximum allowed number of aircrafts under maintenance at the same time.

3.2 Arc expressions and transition guards:

In what follows, the transition guards and arc expressions of the proposed CPN are presented. The arcs in the proposed CPN that link places and transitions have a weight equal to one, meaning that each transition needs one token from each input place in order to fire and produces one token at each output place. The expressions associated with arcs, denoted as $e(p, t)$ or $e(t, p)$, define token flow and updates of values. In particular, expressions associated with input arcs $e(p, t)$ represent token consumption, describing how tokens in the source places can enable and fire the transition. On the other hand, expressions associated with output arcs $e(t, p)$ determine how tokens are generated or have their values updated in the destination places.

Guard and Arcs of transition ν_1 : The transition ν_1 is responsible for removing the aircraft token τ_{a_i} from the operational place p_1 and placing it in the grounded place p_2 . This transition is fired when the utilization clock of any of the tasks reaches its respective maximum operational time interval, i.e., $c_{ij}(t) = f_{ij}$. Moreover, we define the utility cost $J_i(t)$ for each aircraft to further control this transition and dictate the maintenance strategy of the aircraft fleet as follows:

$$J_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^n y_{ij}(t)(c_{ij}(t)/f_{ij}) \cdot w_{ij}, \forall i \in 1, \dots, m \quad (8)$$

where w_{ij} are weights associated with each task and it holds that $\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} = 1, \forall i \in [1, m]$. Then, ν_1 is fired when the following condition holds:

$$g(\nu_1) : J_i(t) > J_{thr} \quad \vee \quad \exists j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : c_{ij}(t) = f_{ij}, \quad (9)$$

where J_{thr} is a threshold expressing the aircraft maintenance policy. Therefore, the likelihood of an aircraft being grounded to execute a maintenance project depends on three parameters: (i) the number of enabled maintenance tasks, (ii) how much utilization time $c_{ij}(t)$ has passed comparatively to the maximum operational time interval f_{ij} of the enabled tasks, and (iii) the importance weight w_{ij} of the enabled tasks. The transition ν_1 consumes the airplane token τ_{a_i} , from the operational place p_1 and transfers the token values $\langle a_i, c_i(t), \delta_i \rangle$ using the input arc expression $e(p_1, \nu_1)$. The output arc expression $e(\nu_1, p_2)$ generates one token τ_{a_i} in the output place p_2 , signifying that aircraft a_i is grounded and ready to schedule its maintenance project.

Arcs of transitions $\nu_{2j} \in T_2$: Transition ν_{2j} represents the selection of task k_j for the current maintenance project $r_i(t)$ of aircraft a_i via updating the parameter values h_{ij} . It is enabled whenever an aircraft token τ_{a_i} is present in the place p_2 and no other condition guards this transition. Transition ν_{2j} consumes token τ_{k_j} from place p_{3j} and generates it back in the same place with updated parameter h_{ij} , depending on whether the j^{th} task is enabled for aircraft a_i and consequently included in the upcoming maintenance project $r_i(t)$:

$$e(\nu_{2j}, p_{3j}) : \langle k_j, h_{ij} \rangle \mapsto \begin{cases} \langle k_j, d_{ij} \rangle, & b_{ij}f_{ij} \leq c_{ij}(t) \\ \langle k_j, 0 \rangle, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Guard and Arcs of transition ν_3 : Transition ν_3 is responsible for removing the aircraft token τ_{a_i} from the grounded place p_2 and placing it in the maintenance place p_4 , as long as there is available maintenance capacity. Thus, transition ν_3 is fired when the following condition holds:

$$g(\nu_3) : \zeta > 0. \quad (11)$$

When transition ν_3 is fired, it consumes the aircraft token τ_{a_i} using the input arc expression $e(p_2, \nu_3)$ and generates it in the output place p_4 , with updated duration parameter signifying the duration of the formed maintenance project $r_i(t)$ as follows:

$$e(\nu_3, p_4) : \langle a_i, c_i(t), \delta_i \rangle \mapsto \langle a_i, c_{ij}(t), \sum_j^n h_{ij} \rangle. \quad (12)$$

Moreover, transition ν_3 , is connected to place p_5 via a pair of input and output arcs to update the maintenance availability and specifically decrease its value by one with this output arc expression $e(\nu_3, p_5) : \langle \zeta \rangle \mapsto \langle \zeta - 1 \rangle$.

Guards and Arcs of transition ν_4 : The transition ν_4 controls the movement of the aircraft token τ_{a_i} from the under maintenance state p_4 back to the operational state p_1 . This transition is fired if the following condition holds:

$$g(\nu_4) : \delta_i \leq 0. \quad (13)$$

The above guard guarantees that aircraft a_i will only return to the operational state after the completion of its maintenance project. When transition ν_4 fires, at time t , the time of last completion of all enabled tasks k_j , included in the executed project r_i , is updated, i.e., $q_{ij} = t$. Therefore, the corresponding utilization clocks of token $\tau_{a_i} = \langle a_i, c_i(t), \delta_i \rangle$ for all enabled tasks are reset to zero, i.e. $c_{ij} = 0$, using the output arc expression $e(\nu_4, p_1)$. Transition ν_4 is also connected to place p_5 via a pair of input and output arcs to update maintenance availability and specifically increase it by one using the following output arc expression $e(\nu_4, p_5) : \langle \zeta \rangle \mapsto \langle \zeta + 1 \rangle$.

Arcs of transition ν_5 : Transition ν_5 consumes aircraft token τ_{a_i} and generates it back in the operational place p_1 with updated values to indicate the progression of time in the operational state. Therefore, the utilization clocks of all tasks are incremented by one at each time step, using the output arc expression $e(\nu_5, p_1) : \langle a_i, c_i(t), \delta_i \rangle \mapsto \langle a_i, c_i(t) + 1, \delta_i \rangle, \forall j \in [1, n]$ where 1 denotes a vector of ones with the same dimension as $c_i(t)$.

Guards and Arcs of transition ν_6 : Similarly, transition ν_6 controls the progression of time under maintenance for the i^{th} aircraft that executes the maintenance project $r_i(t)$. This transition is fired if the following condition holds:

$$g(\nu_6) : \delta_i > 0. \quad (14)$$

Transition ν_6 consumes aircraft token τ_{a_i} and generates it back in the maintenance place p_4 with updated values to indicate the progression of time executing the project. For that reason the following output arc expression is utilized, $e(\nu_6, p_4) : \langle a_i, c_{ij}(t), \delta_i \rangle \mapsto \langle a_i, c_{ij}(t), \delta_i - 1 \rangle$.

Having defined the structure of the CPN, we can utilize it as a DT to evaluate different maintenance strategies for the aircraft fleet. Hence, the proposed framework can model long-term operational dynamics of an aircraft fleet, simulate diverse maintenance policy configurations, and evaluate both static and adaptive strategies under realistic and disruption-prone conditions.

4. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

This section presents the experimental setup and evaluation of the proposed DT framework for the problem of aircraft fleet maintenance scheduling. All experiments were conducted in a controlled simulation environment, replicating real-world fleet maintenance constraints, operational requirements, and workload variability. The simulations were implemented in Python, leveraging the SNAKES Petri Net library¹. We follow the work in (Deng et al. (2020)) and define the following four performance metrics for each aircraft a_i , considering the entire time horizon: (a) operation time of an aircraft in the entire horizon denoted by o_i , (b) Utilization Rate denoted by U that is the ratio of operational days to the total time horizon per aircraft, and averaged across the fleet, i.e., $U = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{o_i}{T}$,

¹ <https://pypi.org/project/SNAKES/>

Table 1. Maintenance Statistics over J_{thr} .

J_{thr}	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
ANME	10.2	7.5	6.9	6.7	6.5	6.5	6.3	6.3	6.3	6.3
Grounded Days	50.4	37.3	19.5	7.1	10.6	10.0	14.7	12.5	12.5	12.5
Mean Days in Maintenance	40.7	35.2	34.6	34.0	33.5	33.6	33.1	33.1	33.0	33.0
Mean Project Duration	3.0	3.7	4.0	4.1	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.3

(c) total unused operational time for all tasks denoted by λ_i , which quantifies the distance (in terms of days) between the maximum allowable operational time interval f_{ij} and the respective utilization clock $c_{ij}(t)$, each time aircraft a_i is grounded to execute maintenance task k_j . We also define the overall maintenance cost as follows:

$$C = \xi_1 \sum_{t=t_0}^H \sum_{i=1}^m x_i(t) + \xi_2 \sum_{t=t_0}^H \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - c_{ij}(t)) \cdot x_i(t). \quad (15)$$

The simulation parameters are provided by Aegean Airlines based on their operational data. Specifically, we consider a fleet of $m = 68$ aircraft with $n = 1039$ individual maintenance tasks with random initial utilization clock values $c_{ij}(t_0)$. Moreover, the minimum utilization thresholds and the weights of each task for each aircraft are drawn from a uniform distribution, i.e., $b_{ij} \sim \mathcal{U}(0.6, 0.9)$, $w_{ij} \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$. The frequencies f_{ij} are approximately normally distributed, with a mean of 1,490 days and a standard deviation of 210 days, while the task durations d_{ij} follow a log-normal distribution with a mean of approximately 0.11 days. Finally, for the cost weights of Eq. (15), we selected $\xi_1 = 0.7$ and $\xi_2 = 0.3$. All of the results are averaged over 20 simulation runs.

4.1 Experiment A - Static maintenance policies

The first experiment examines the long-term performance of a range of static maintenance scheduling policies in a disruption-free environment emulated by the DT. Specifically, in this setup, we evaluate different values of J_{thr} (see Eq. (9)) for a time horizon of $H = 1000$ days and the maximum number of aircraft simultaneously under-maintenance is $L = 5$. Lower values of J_{thr} of Eq. (9) correspond to more conservative maintenance policies, wherein relatively few tasks are enabled and scheduled well before reaching their operational limits. In contrast, higher values of J_{thr} represent less conservative maintenance policies, wherein a greater number of maintenance tasks must be enabled before being eligible for maintenance scheduling, thus prioritizing the operational utilization.

As presented in Fig. 2, the total maintenance cost C declines sharply when the policy threshold increases. This result is evident, as higher thresholds delay maintenance events, reducing unused operational time and thus lowering the total cost. Specifically, the cost curve exhibits a near-exponential decrease on a logarithmic scale, achieving almost 99% reduction when $J_{thr} = 1$ compared to $J_{thr} = 0.1$. Similarly, the utilization rate percentage U , initially increases with higher policy thresholds, indicating that aircraft are available for operational use more consistently. However, this trend reaches a plateau at

Fig. 2. Impact of J_{thr} on Maintenance Cost C and Utilization Rate U .

$J_{thr} = 0.4$, beyond which further increases in the threshold do not significantly enhance operational availability, remaining on average at $U = 0.95$. This also aligns with the Mean Time Between Maintenance events (MTBM), defined as the average number of operational days between two maintenance events, and averaged for the entire fleet. In Fig. 3, MTBM demonstrates diminishing returns beyond $J_{thr} = 0.4$, averaging 146 days for the rest of the policies. Moreover, Fig. 3 presents the Average Number of Maintenance Events (ANME) averaged for the entire fleet, which decreases to 6.3 events for the whole time horizon at $J_{thr} = 1$, having almost a 38% reduction compared to $J_{thr} = 0.1$. Table 1 summarizes the results for different policy thresholds averaged over the entire fleet for the whole horizon. Interestingly, the mean number of grounded days per aircraft attains its lowest values at policy thresholds of 0.4, 0.5, and 0.6. This can be attributed to the fact that these thresholds facilitate groupings of maintenance tasks that, within the context of the observed period, prove to be particularly advantageous. Thus, the temporal distribution of the formed projects minimizes competition among aircraft for maintenance availability and reduces the days spent grounded. Perhaps a more notable observation is that the mean grounded days significantly decrease and reach 12.5 days for the entire horizon for higher policy thresholds, while the mean project duration for the entire fleet increases to 4.27 days, signifying that maintenance tasks are executed in parallel by forming a single maintenance project. As a result, it is evident that higher policy thresholds minimize the total cost and reduce the number of maintenance events, thus increasing the operational capabilities of the aircraft fleet.

4.2 Experiment B - Adaptive Policy Strategies

The second experiment resembles a real-world scenario with stochastic unscheduled maintenance events. Specifically, for each day of the maintenance horizon of $H = 300$ days, we selected randomly the number of unscheduled maintenance events drawn by a Bernoulli-modulated (capped) Poisson distribution ($\lambda = 3.0$). These unscheduled events could be either aircrafts from another aviation company requesting maintenance or urgent unexpected failures causing an aircraft to be grounded due to unplanned mechanical or operational disruptions. The maximum number of aircraft simultaneously under maintenance is $L = 4$. To evaluate such a scenario, three distinct

Fig. 3. Impact of J_{thr} on Average Number of Maintenance Events and Mean Time Between Maintenance (MTBM).

strategies are compared using the proposed DT, namely (a) Static, (b) Over-Reactive and (c) Semi-Reactive. The Static strategy applies the best cost-effective policy threshold as identified in the first experiment across the entire horizon, without accounting for disruptions. The Over-Reactive strategy recalculates the optimal policy threshold at every time step in which a failure occurs. Finally, the Semi-Reactive Strategy is updated only in response to a failure that causes the number of aircrafts simultaneously under maintenance to exceed the predefined limit L , thus triggering constraint Eq. (6). Fig. 4 illustrates the total Cumulative Maintenance Cost (C) over the horizon. The DT achieves the lowest cost when emulating the Semi-Reactive Strategy, achieving 17.15% and 22.31% cost reduction compared to the Over-Reactive and Static strategies, respectively. Moreover, the Over-Reactive strategy achieved better than the Static one; however, while this approach ensures maximum responsiveness, it also leads to overly sensitive policy recalculations that overcompensate for isolated disruptive events. Finally, naturally, the Static policy fails to adapt the maintenance schedule to abrupt changes, highlighting the need for a DT and a modelling approach that can incorporate both proactive and reactive policies in the context of aircraft maintenance as a service. Lastly, a key result is that the Semi-Reactive strategy provides the best results for the aviation operations, by ensuring prudent and adaptive maintenance schedules without risking operational availability of the fleet.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we present a novel DT framework, leveraging CPNs to model and simulate the complex operational dynamics of aircraft maintenance scheduling. The proposed DT enables planning and dynamic adaptation to scheduling disruptions. Simulation results highlight the capability of the proposed CPN framework to simulate and assess different scheduling policies and adaptive strategies. Regarding our future plans, we will employ model predictive control techniques to achieve fine-grained solutions for the maintenance scheduling of the aircraft fleet and evaluate different policies with the proposed DT.

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